

ROLE OF FETUIN-A AND HSCRP IN CVD RISK IN HYPOTHYROIDISM IRAQI WOMEN

Ali Abdullateef Albayati* and Ali Abdul Rasool Hussein

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, College of Medicine, Mustansiriyah University, Iraq.

*e-mail : ali_abd54144@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT : Hypothyroidism is one of the common endocrine disorders that is associated with cardiovascular diseases, it is more common in women with female: male ratio reaches up to 6:1. Hypothyroidism could be regarded as inflammatory condition and Systemic inflammation was emerged as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease. To study the association of serum levels of fetuin-A with TSH, FT4, T4, T3 and hsCRP as an inflammatory marker 46 patients aged ≥ 30 years were consecutively selected after have been diagnosed as hypothyroidism. Healthy (N = 42), age and sex-matched subjects as controls. Clinical characteristics were recorded and serum levels of lipid profile, fetuin-A, TSH, FT4, T4, T3 and hsCRP were measured. Fetuin-A was significantly decreased in hypothyroid individuals while, hsCRP, LDL-c and atherogenic index were significantly higher in the same group compared with control. No significant correlations were observed for Fetuin-A or hsCRP with thyroid function test and classical lipid profile measure. However, atherogenic index showed highly significant correlations with TSH. The results of our study showed that all aspects of increasing risk factors of cardiovascular disease were observed in newly diagnosed Iraqi women with hypothyroidism represented by; increase systemic inflammation, disarranged lipid profile and an increasing vascular calcification risk.

Key words : Fetuin-A, hsCRP, hypothyroidism.

INTRODUCTION

Disorder of thyroid function is a common endocrine condition, that affects all age groups with an increasing the risk with being and female sex (Canaris *et al*, 2000). Hypothyroidism represents the most common thyroid gland disorders worldwide and it is characterised by low level of thyroid hormones that results from iodine deficiency or gland destruction by autoimmunity or surgery or radiation (Abid *et al*, 2016). Hypothyroidism is more common in women with female: male ratio reach up to 6:1 and clinically classified into overt and subclinical hypothyroidism based clinical features and biochemical thyroid hormones function profile (Duntas and Yen, 2019)

Being impaired thyroid function is actually associated with disturbed lipid profile (Oh *et al*, 2018). Furthermore, the risk of heart failure and cerebrovascular accidents CVA had been increased and shown to be associated with hypothyroidism. furthermore, dyslipidemias per se cannot explain the whole pathogenesis of vascular abnormality (Cappola *et al*, 2019). Systemic inflammation was emerged as risk factors for cardiovascular disease. High-sensitive C-reactive protein (hs-CRP) is an acute-

phase reactant that represents a marker of subclinical inflammation, and shown to be as an independent predictor of atherosclerosis (Ridker, 2004). Hypothyroidism could be regarded as inflammatory condition as it is associated with serum inflammatory factors such as (CRP), (TNF- α) and (IL-6) (Mancini *et al*, 2016). Furthermore, Marchiori *et al* (2015) showed that, there is a decrease proinflammatory mediators and enhancement of anti-inflammatory mediators in response to thyroxin therapy for hypothyroid patients.

Vascular Calcification is another factor shown to be involved in cardiovascular risk. Hypothyroid state shown to be associated with coronary artery calcification (Bakiner *et al*, 2014). Moreover, physiological level of thyroid hormones was demonstrated to inhibit vascular complications by inhibits expression of mediator involved vascular calcification (Sato *et al*, 2005).

Fetuin-A is a plasma glycoprotein synthesized by the liver and in many studies been implicated in different metabolic and vascular events like inhibition of ectopic calcification and inhibition of cardiovascular complication (Schäfer *et al*, 2003). In addition, low serum level of